

Benchmarking the Impact of MRI Data Preprocessing on Deep CNN Models Performance for Brain Tumor Detection and Classification

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ABSTRACT

Brain tumor detection and classification are the most difficult tasks in medical images analyzing using deep CNNs. Most of the time CNN models fail to achieve high accuracy due to noise and other artifacts in MRI images. Therefore, it is necessary to improve images quality by applying different preprocessing techniques before training of the models. In this study, we applied three common preprocessing techniques like non-local means for denoising, Otsu thresholding for skull stripping, and contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization for contrast enhancement. This paper presents a comparative performance analysis of two CNN architectures, including AlexNet and VGG16 before and after preprocessing of the data. By using a dataset of 7023 MRI images across four categories (glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and nontumor), the experimental results revealed that the proposed models after preprocessing of the data achieved the highest accuracy 95% for AlexNet and 97% for VGG16. In other hand, these models before preprocessing of the data obtained lower accuracy, at 89%. The results show that applying preprocessing techniques to MRI brain tumor images before training significantly improves the accuracy of CNN models.

Keywords: Brain tumor, MRI, Pre-processing, CNNs, AlexNet, VGG16.

INTRODUCTION

Medical images are widely used in diagnosing various diseases, with the help of these images' doctors can detect the presence of diseases in human body. Brain tumors with the common types like glioma, meningioma and pituitary are one of the destructive diseases which damage the brain tissues of human and endanger the lives [1,2]. Brain tumors can be cancerous (which originates in another part of the body and spread to the brain via breast cancer, kidney cancer, or skin cancer) and not cancerous (which originates in the brain and develops from the brain cells, nerve cells, or glands) [3,4]. The examination of MRI images by the doctor plays a fundamental role in determining the type of brain tumor. Diagnosis consists of distinguishing brain tissue from malignant tumors, which is done after comparing the tumor and classifying it as benign and malignant based on its characteristics. To diagnose this abnormality, the patient is given the fact that the comparison between

the healthy hemisphere and the tumor is not symmetrical. Magnetic resonance imaging is an advanced medical method for producing high-resolution images of human body organs, detecting abnormalities, and monitoring the progression of lesions. Ultimately, the features obtained from these images are used for direct identification and classification of glands and tumors [5, 6, 7]. In the past few years, researchers applied artificial intelligence especially machine learning and deep learning for brain tumor detection and classification to achieve better accuracy [8]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are the type of deep learning used for analysis of the data, such as images. It built up from a series of layers with particular responsibilities. In general, the inputs represent pixel values of the images entering the networks, convolution layers employ filters to recognize specific pattern and features of images. ReLu is one of the mechanisms to bring non-linearity in a model. Pooling layers reduce the size of the convolved features in order to make

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more efficient subsequent computations. Flattening simply reshapes the output into a vector of a given fixed size; the fully connected layers utilize high-level

feature maps to help in decision making [9, 10]. The CNN architecture is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CNN Architecture

This paper makes the following contributions:

- Proposing a Deep CNN-based models for automatically detecting and classifying brain tumors in MRI images.
- Analysing and validating of the impact of preprocessing techniques on the performance of CNNs models such as VGG16 and AlexNet.
- Analysing and comparing the performance of VGG16 and AlexNet models before preprocessing and after preprocessing of data for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images.

Figure 2 presents an outline of the primary concepts in this study. The first section 1 introduces brain and brain tumor, MRI images of brain tumor and the CNN. In section 2 we reviewed existing literature on brain tumor using various deep CNNs models. Section 3 describes materials and methods where we explained the dataset, proposed CNNs-based models and evaluation metrics for this work. Section 4 covered performance analysis and discussion of the CNNs models, and finally, section 5 summarized this study and offered some future research directions in this field of study.

Figure 2. Outline of this research paper

1. Related work

In this section we have reviewed recent studies using deep CNNs for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. In table 1 we have summarized some previous studies.

Muntahaa and Tauheed. [11] suggested pre-trained VGG16 using transfer learning for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. In this study two publicly available datasets Kaggle and Figshare were used which contain 3264 MRI images. Preprocessing techniques like resizing, normalization,

data augmentation, and handling of class imbalance through weights and oversampling. The fine-tuned VGG16 model achieved 85% accuracy. Moreno et al. [12] introduced a deep learning-based framework using convolutional neural networks for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. The proposed CNN model was trained on a dataset of 9147 MRI images categorized into glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor classes. Preprocessing techniques such as image resizing, normalization, and data augmentation were applied to improve generalization and reduce overfitting. Experimental results shown that the model achieved 86.17% accuracy. Khan et al. [13] proposed a hybrid CNNs model for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. They utilized 400 MRI images collected from Bahawal Victoria Hospital (Pakistan). Pre-processing techniques like Gaussian denoising, image sharpening, and skull stripping used to improve accuracy across multiple datasets. They applied a fused feature optimization approach and tested two machine learning classifiers convolutional neural network (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). The suggested CNN model achieved overall accuracy of 84.5%, TP rate of 0.845, and ROC of 0.897, while LSTM achieved 83.71% accuracy. Smitha et al. [14] suggested a comprehensive deep CNNs hybrid models for brain tumor detection and classification. They used 100 MRI images collected from BRATS platform. Preprocessing techniques like normalization, skull stripping, and anisotropic diffusion applied to improve image quality and reduce noise. They combined CNNs with traditional machine learning methods such as SVM and Mask R-CNN. The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 92.3%. Mahmud et al. [15] presented a comparative analysis of deep learning models for brain tumor detection

using MRI, with a focus on a custom-built CNN architecture. The study utilized a dataset of 3264 MRI images, categorized into four classes: glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and no tumor. The images were pre-processed with Gaussian and Laplacian filters, The proposed CNN achieved accuracy of 93.3%, and transfer learning models such as ResNet-50 81.1%, VGG16 71.6%, and Inception V3 80%. Zebari et al. [16] developed a DenseNet121 architecture for brain tumor detection and classification model based on the impact of data augmentation and preprocessing on improving CNNs model performance accuracy using MRI images. This study applied 250 MRI images collected from Kaggle which increased by data augmentation to 1771 images. Pre-processing techniques like denoising with Gaussian filtering and normalization have used by the authors. On the augmented dataset the model achieved testing accuracy of 94.83%. Khan et al. [17] proposed a hierarchical deep learning model for detecting and classifying brain tumors using CNNs to enhance the accuracy for four classes like glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and no-tumor. This study used 3264 MRI images from Kaggle for implementation. Pre-processing techniques like normalization and resizing used to standardized the images and the proposed model achieved an overall validation accuracy of 92.13%. Brindha et al. [18], proposed a comparative performance of an artificial neural network (ANN) and a convolutional neural network (CNN) for the binary classification of brain MRI images. This study applied 2065 MRI images collected from GitHub and used resizing preprocessing technique to standardize the images for implantation. The proposed CNN achieved accuracy of 89% and ANN achieved test accuracy of 65.21%,

Table 1. Summary of Literature Review

Reference	Year	Dataset Used	Technique Used	Classification Type	Accuracy
Muntahaa and Tauheed [11]	2025	3264 MRI images	Pre-trained VGG16, Data augmentation like rotation, flipping, zoom.	Multi-class	85%
Moreno et al. [12]	2025	9147 MRI images	Pre-trained models like VGG16, DenseNet121, Inception and ResNet-v2	Multi-class	86.17%
Khan et al. [13]	2024	400 MRI images	CNNs, LSTM networks, Gaussian filtering, sharpening, skull stripping), Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM)	Multi-class	84.50%
Smitha et al. [14]	2024	100 MRI images	Combined SVM and Mask R-CNN outputs via thresholding and post-processing.	Binary-Class	92.3%

Mahmud et al. [15]	2023	3264 MRI images	A custom CNN and Transfer Learning models including ResNet-50, VGG16, and Inception V3.	Multi-class	93.30%
Zebari et al. [16]	2023	253 MRI images	DenseNet121, Resizing, Gaussian Filter Denoising, Normalization, Data Augmentation like Rotation, Shearing.	Binary-Class	94.83%
Khan et al. [17]	2022	3264 MRI images	Custom convolutional neural network	Multi-class	92.13%
Brindha et al. [18]	2021	2065 MRI images	Custom Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	Binary-Class	89%, 65%

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section presents the collection of the dataset, preprocessing techniques used, as well as the CNN models for brain tumor detection and classification using MRI images.

3.1 Dataset Description

We have trained and tested two CNN models (AlexNet and VGG16 on brain tumor MRI images) before and after pre-processing of the dataset in this work. The dataset obtained from publicly accessible online data on Kaggle.com which comprises 7023

MRI images partitioned as two subsets for training and testing where each subset contains labeled images corresponding to four classes like meningioma, glioma, pituitary, and no-tumor are shown in Figure 3.

Image dataset comes with 7023 MRI images, a total of 5712 images were used in the training subset and 1311 images were used in the testing subset. Images from both subsets were mixed for experimentation with 80 % of data as training and 20% testing. Images in the dataset were Gray-scale with different resolutions. A detailed overview of the dataset is provided in Table 2.

Figure 3. Forms of Brain Tumor Images

Table 2. Overview of the provided dataset

Labelled	Number of Images		Format	Type
Glioma	Training	1321	JPG	Grayscale
	Testing	300		

Meningioma	Training	1339	JPG	Grayscale
	Testing	306		
No-tumor	Training	1595	JPG	Grayscale
	Testing	405		
Pituitary	Training	1457	JPG	Grayscale
	Testing	300		

3.2 Preprocessing Techniques

Image pre-processing is an important step in image analysis and computer vision tasks. It involves applying a series of techniques to raw images to improve their quality, enhance specific features, or transform them into a format suitable for further analysis or machine learning models. There are many techniques for preprocessing to improve the quality of

the images to improving deep learning model performance accuracy, particularly in medical image analysis like brain tumor detection, classification. We have used non-local means (NLM) denoising, Otsu thresholding and contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) image pre-processing techniques for our work. Figure 4 represents the block diagram of the proposed pre-processing method [19,20].

Figure 4. Block Diagram of the Proposed Pre-processing Methods

3.2.1 Non-Local Means (NLM) denoising

Non-local means (NLM) denoising is an advanced image processing technique used to reduce noise in images while preserving fine details and edges. It was introduced by Antoni Buades, Bartomeu Coll, and Jean-Michel Morel in 2005. The key idea behind NLM is to exploit the redundancy of information in an image, meaning that similar patterns or structures often appear in different parts of the image [21].

Figure 5 shows the original noisy image and pre-processed image using NLM technique. The mathematical formulation for NLM method is as follows:

$$NLU(p) = \frac{1}{c(p)} \int f(d(B(p), B(q)))u(q)dq \quad (1)$$

where,

$NLu(p)$ = denoised pixel value at position p .

$C(p)$ = normalization factor ensuring weights sum to 1.

$B(p)$ and $B(q)$ are patches (small neighborhoods) centered around pixels.

$d(B(p), B(q))$ is similarity measure (Euclidean distance) between patches $B(p)$ and $B(q)$.

$f(d(B(p), B(q)))$ is a weighting function, typically an exponential decay function:

$$f(d(B(p), B(q))) = e^{-\frac{(d(B(p), B(q)))}{h^2}}$$

where h is a filtering parameter that controls the decay rate

$u(q)$ is the intensity (grayscale or RGB) value of the pixel at q

$d(q)$ represents the integral over the whole search region (in continuous space)

Figure 5. (a) Noisy Image with Rician Noise, (b) Denoised Image with NLM [26]

3.2.2 Otsu Thresholding Method

Otsu thresholding is a global thresholding technique used in image processing to automatically determine the optimal threshold value for binarizing an image. It minimizes the intra-class variance (the variance within foreground and background pixel groups), effectively separating an image into two classes: foreground (object) and background [19]. Figure 6 shows the original image and pre-processed image using Otsu thresholding technique.

The mathematical formulation for Otsu's method is as follows:

$$I_{skul-stripped}(x, y) = I(x, y) \cdot 1(I(x, y) > t^*) \quad (2)$$

where,

$I_{skul-stripped}(x, y)$ is the skull-stripped MRI image

$I(x, y)$ is the intensity of the pixel at location (x, y) .

$t^* = \operatorname{argmax}_t P_0(t)P_1(t)(m_0(t) - m_1(t))^2$ is the Otsu threshold.

$1(I(x, y) > t^*)$ is the indicator function, which is 1 if $I(x, y) > t^*$ (brain region) and 0 otherwise (skull/background).

This formula first determines t^* , then applies thresholding using an indicator function, and finally multiplies the original image with the binary mask to retain only the brain region.

Figure 6. (a) Original Image, (b) Skull Stripped Image [26]

3.2.3 Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE):

Contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) is an image processing technique used to enhance the contrast of an image. Unlike traditional histogram equalization, CLAHE works on small regions of the image, called tiles, rather than processing the entire image at once. This adaptive approach adjusts the contrast in each tile individually by computing a histogram-based transformation specific to that region. The contrast within each tile is modified, and the adjusted values are blended with neighbouring tiles to ensure a smooth transition and avoid artificial boundaries. Additionally, CLAHE limits the contrast enhancement in uniform areas to prevent excessive noise amplification that might be

present in the image [22]. Figure 7 shows the original image and pre-processed image using CLAHE technique. The contrast in an image is calculated using the following equation:

$$P_x(i) = P(x=i) = \frac{n_i}{n} \Rightarrow 0 \leq i < L \quad (3)$$

where,

$P_x(i)$ is the probability of a pixel having intensity i , x is the pixel intensity value in a grayscale image, i is the specific intensity level (from 0 to $L - 1$), L is the total number of intensity levels (usually 256 for an 8-bit image), n_i is the number of pixels in the image with intensity i . n is the total number of pixels in the image

Figure 7. (a) Original Image, (b) Enhanced image [26]

3.3 The Architectures of the Proposed CNNs

In this work we have used AlexNet and VGG16 for training and classifying the MRI images and were implemented on the collected data before pre-processing and after the pre-processing.

3.3.1 AlexNet

[AlexNet](#), developed by Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey Hinton, is a landmark model that won the ImageNet Large-Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) in 2012. It

introduced several innovative ideas that shaped the future of CNNs. AlexNet consists of 8 layers, including 5 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers. It uses traditional stacked convolutional layers with max-pooling in between. Its deep network

structure allows for the extraction of complex features from images. The input image size for AlexNet is $224 \times 224 \times 3$. [23,24]. In figure 8, the AlexNet model architecture is shown.

Figure 8. AlexNet model architecture.

3.3.3 VGG16

Visual geometry group network is the full form of VGGNet which is CNN architecture for implementing deep learning models performance. It was able to perform second in the ImageNet large scale visual recognition challenge (ILSVRC) competition that was completed in 2014. VGG16 and VGG19 are the common models of VGGNet. We

have used VGG16 model in this work, which has minor modifications from the VGGNet and it has 16 convolutional layers, five max-pooling layers, and three fully connected(dense) layers. Also different from the original architecture, the classifier namely softmax is substituted by the support vector machine classifier in the modified architecture [24, 25]. The input image size for VGG16 is $224 \times 224 \times 3$. In figure 9, the architecture of VGG16 is shown.

Figure 9. VGG16 model architecture

3.4 Parameters for training of proposed models

Parameters are the internal variables which control how the models process the data and makes predications. The models were trained for 10 epochs with a batch size of 32. Data augmentation techniques,

including rotation and flipping also were applied to improve generalization. Table 3 lists the proposed models input and training parameters.

Table 3. Parameters for training of the proposed models.

Parameters	Values
Input shape	$224 \times 224 \times 3$
Batch size	32
Number of epochs	10
Number of training samples	5712
Number of test samples	1311
Output classes	4
Class mode	Categorical (multi-class classification)
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.0001
Activation function	ReLU, SoftMax

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section Presents the performance and results of the models which trained and tested on the proposed dataset before and after applying the preprocessing techniques on the brain tumor MRI dataset for brain tumor detection and classification.

4.1 Experimental Setup

The experiments were implemented using python 3.12 programming language with several libraries such as Tensorflow, Keras, Numpy, Pandas, Matplotlib, Sklearn, OS, on Google Colab platform, utilizing GPU T4 with high-capacity RAM to enable efficient and reproducible analyses. the models are trained with the Keras framework using the TensorFlow backend. Graphs depicting the predictive performance over 10 epochs show the x-axis representing epochs and the y-axis indicating accuracy and loss. The performance of the models also summarized in confusion metrics, where rows

represent the predicted classification targets and columns represent the actual classes from the training dataset.

4.2 Accuracy and Lose Curve

Accuracy and lose curves are graphical representations used to monitor the performance of a model during the training process. They help in diagnosing issues like overfitting or underfitting and in determining when to stop training. These curves typically plot accuracy and loss over epochs (iterations of the training process) for both the training and validation datasets. Figures 10 and 11 show the evaluation of the accuracy and loss curve during the training and validation periods of the proposed models before and after preprocessing of the dataset images

Figure 10. Accuracy and Lose Curve of AlexNet model (a) before pre-processing of the data, (b) after pre-processing of the data.

Figure 11. Accuracy and Lose Curve of VGG16 model (a) before pre-processing of the data, (b) after pre-processing of the data

4.3 Confusion Matrix

It is a tabular form which represent the results of the prediction of the classification carried out and compare among correct and false results of

predictions and show that which cases confused by the models. Confusion matrix classified the results into four categories like true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP) and false negative (FN). Table 6 shown the elements of confusion matrix.

Table 6. Confusion Matix Elements

Element	Description
TP	Image with tumor correctly classified by model as a tumor
NP	Image without tumor correctly classified as not tumor
FP	Model classifies image with tumor but it not contains tumor
FN	Model classifies images without tumor but image contains tumor

The confusion metrics in figures 12 and 13 illustrate the performance of the proposed models before and after preprocessing of the data in detecting and classifying MRI images into four categories: glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and no-tumor. The targeted class is represented in the X-direction and the output

class is represented in the Y-direction accordingly. According to the results of the values got by the confusion matrix in figure 12, it shows that the AlexNet model before pre-processing of the data confused and misclassified the cases while AlexNet

after preprocessing of the data classified most of the cases correctly and has better performance.

Figure 12. Confusion matrices of AlexNet model. (a) Before preprocessing of the data. (b) After preprocessing of the data.

In other hand, in figure 13 the confusion matrix illustrates that the VGG16 model before preprocessing of the data confused and misclassified

most of the cases but after preprocessing of the proposed data this model correctly detects and classify most of the cases.

Figure 13. Confusion matrices of VGG16 model. (a) Before preprocessing of the data. (b) After preprocessing of the data.

4.4 Performance Analysis

The performance of models evaluated by the equations such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score by using True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP) and False Negative (FN) for each class in the classification problem. The proposed modes achieved test accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores before and after pre-processing of the data summarized in tables 4 and 5.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \tag{4}$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \tag{5}$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \tag{6}$$

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \tag{7}$$

$$F1 - Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \tag{8}$$

Our experimental results show that the performance of the proposed models AlexNet and VGG16 after pre-processing of the data is better than the same models which implemented in the dataset before preprocessing. Tables 4 and 5 illustrate that the

models with pre-processed data achieved high accuracy rate of AlexNet (95%) and VGG16 (97%) while these models without pre-processed data achieved lower accuracy 89%.

Table 4. Performance Analysis of AlexNet Model

Before Preprocessing of the Data				
Type of Tumor	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Glioma	0.95	0.91	0.93	89%
Meningioma	0.94	0.96	0.95	
No-tumor	0.94	0.69	0.79	
Pituitary	0.75	0.97	0.85	
After Preprocessing of the Data				
Type of Tumor	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Glioma	0.93	0.97	0.95	95%
Meningioma	0.98	0.96	0.97	
No-tumor	0.92	0.92	0.92	
Pituitary	0.95	0.93	0.94	

Table 5. Performance Analysis of VGG16 Model

Before Preprocessing of the Data				
Type of Tumor	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Glioma	0.86	0.99	0.92	89%
Meningioma	0.96	1.00	0.98	
No-tumor	0.77	0.89	0.83	
Pituitary	1.00	0.65	0.79	
After Preprocessing of the Data				
Type of Tumor	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Glioma	0.99	0.95	0.97	97%
Meningioma	0.99	1.00	0.99	
No-tumor	0.78	0.98	0.87	
Pituitary	1.00	0.76	0.87	

CONCLUSION

In this study we have shown the impact of pre-processing of data on the performance of CNNs models for brain tumor detection and classification using MRI images. We implemented and evaluated two CNN architecture like AlexNet and VGG16 on the Kaggle publicly available dataset which contain

7023 MRI images across four classes like glioma, meningioma, pituitary and no-tumor before and after preprocessing the data. The results indicate that proposed models after pre-processing of the data have better performance and improved the classification accuracy. Our models with pre-processing of the data achieved high accuracy VGG16 with 97% and AlexNet 95 %, while without preprocessing of the

data both of the proposed models obtained lower accuracy of 89%. However, the analysis of confusion matrices and performance graphs illustrate that the proposed models before preprocessing of the data revealed some challenges, such as misclassification between tumor types and overfitting to the training data. These issues suggest that further improvements are needed to using advanced preprocessing and noise-reduction techniques on the data for improving the quality of the images and enhance model performance.

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